

Research Article

A STUDY ON SOCIAL SKILLS IN RELATION TO OCCUPATIONAL SELF EFFICACY OF PIGEON BREEDERS AT TUTICORIN DISTRICT, TAMIL NADU

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Article History: Received 28th October 2021; Accepted 13th November 2021; Published 15th November 2021

ABSTRACT

Pigeon farming is one of the beneficial sectors for income generation as well as hobby. Present study was conducted to study the difference between social skills and occupational self - efficacy of literate and illiterate pigeon breeders and to study the occurrence of social skills among them. For this purpose a sample of 55 pigeon breeders were randomly selected and interview was conducted among them with the help of pre-structured questionnaire. In this present study findings reported that there was significant difference between social skills and occupational self - efficacy of illiterate and literate pigeon breeders, it was higher in literate pigeon breeders and lower in illiterate pigeon breeders and also out of 5 skills suggested by Springer, 40% were communication skill, 23.64% were problem solving skill, 14.55% were social Awareness, 12.72% were co-operation and 9.09% were responsibility skill which were occurred among the pigeon breeders.

Keywords: Occupational self-efficacy, Pigeon breeders, Pigeon farming, Social skills.

INTRODUCTION

Pigeon farming is very interesting, profitable enterprises and pigeons are very popular domestic bird. Pigeons are considered as the symbol of peace. Here in India due to religious sentiments, this farming has not taken its shape, in our neighbour country like Pakistan, Bangladesh, China the squab raising has become a means of livelihood for the poor rural people. It fetches good money without involving any expenditure. In our country also now the people has started realizing its importance and is becoming more popular day by day, Among tribal people this farming is very popular. Almost all types of people who have facilities, love to raise some pigeon in their home. Pigeon farming require less labor and low investment. Social skills are defined as interpersonal behavior that helps the individual in society. Social skills are the ability to interact with others that are considered as fundamental to human development (Odom *et al.*,1992). Also social skills can be regarded as personality traits or personality capabilities that

contribute to psycho-social outcome. Social skills are essential for every social being. These skills are discrete, observable and teachable that initiate and sustain social interaction that are decently associated to measures of social competence (Dinesh Kumar and Devi, 2018). India is home to the largest population of 287 million illiterate adults in the world. This amounts to 37% of the global total. Literacy constitutes the backbone of development in a progressing country like India. It enhances the quality of life, awareness, and skills of people. Literacy is the ability to read, write and comprehend information in order to communicate effectively. It is empowering and fuels social and human development. Literacy serves as the foundation of basic education for all. The knowledge of social conventions combined with problem-solving capacities of people is what determines them as being literate. In India, while the adult literacy rate is measured for people aged above 15 years, the rate of youth literacy is measured for people aged between 15-24 years. According to the 2011 Census, any person aged seven and above and has the ability to read and write is

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considered literate. The average literacy rate in India stands at 74.04%. A person with strong feeling of efficacy strongly influences a person's achievement. Self efficacy is the measure of one's own abilities to complete tasks and reach goals. According to Albert Bandura, self - efficacy is the belief in one's capabilities to organise and execute the courses of action required to manage prospective situations. In other words, self – efficacy is a person's belief in his or her ability to succeed in a particular situation. Bandura, (1994) described these beliefs as determinants of how people think, behave and feel. Occupational self - efficacy is a specific in affecting the belief systems of different areas of occupation to a different extent.

Mankind has practiced with pigeon keeping about 10,000 years in almost every part of the world (Levi, 1957). Probably pigeon is the first bird species to have been reared by humans. They live side by side with human as a source of food, hobby and experimental purposes (Sari *et al.*, 2008). It has a long productive life and a short reproductive cycle besides its high disease resistance. Because of these above mentioned advantages, pigeon is considered as a ready cash source of income during hard time and provides employment opportunities for villages especially for poor women and educated unemployed youth (El-Hanoun *et al.*, 2008). Chinese people consider pigeon meat as having medicinal value. Squab is often sold much higher prices than other poultry birds. There exists many breeds in Kerala both exotic and indigenous mainly used for fancy purpose as a pet as well as for sports (Kotresh Prasad, 2017). Comparing with other poultry, pigeon able to produce at a very low cost, it require less feed, caring, housing and capital investment (Omar *et al.*, 2014). Pigeon farming is in Tuticorin district is increasing day by day due to profitable income and hobby of pigeon keeping as a pet. This study is conducted to assess the difference between social skills and occupational self - efficacy of literate and illiterate pigeon breeders at Tuticorin district with the help of pre - structured questionnaire as this is one of the emerging live stock enterprises in Tuticorin district.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

For the present study the investigator adapted the descriptive survey method for the collection of the data. Because this method was considered to be more suitable for the present problem. A field study was carried out on 55 randomly selected pigeon breeders in Tuticorin district. Data were collected through semi-structured interview with questionnaire. Data were collected in the year 2018. The collected data included information on details of pigeon breeders including his age, educational qualification, purpose of pigeon keeping, outcomes of pigeon keeping, social skills they possessed, knowledge, attitude and awareness on pigeon diseases etc. The collected data were analysed by using percentages.

Population and Sample

The target population for the study was all the pigeon breeders in Tuticorin, District. In the present study a sample of 55 pigeon breeders (17 illiterate and 38 literate) was drawn through random sampling method.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 shows Occurrence of different social skills among pigeon breeders. Springer listed social skills that needed for successful social interaction in social setting. Among these 5 social skills, communication skill plays a predominant place among the pigeon breeders. Communication skills are ranked among a job candidates “must have” skills according to a 2010 survey conducted by the National Association of College and Employers. Effective communication skill is the most important tool to achieve the desire purpose. Business is a kind of interpersonal communication. The administrator and employees, sellers and buyers must communicate effectively to promote the business. Even a small pigeon seller with his convincing skill attracts more customers to earn more profit. Excellent communication skills are key for every pigeon breeders to navigate upward within the pigeon farming business. Theoretical and technical knowledge about the field is must but it should be coupled with effective communication in order to reap good results. In the present study results reveals that communication skills is an important social skill needed for marketing the pigeons and get more income in this business.

Table 1. Occurrence of different social skills among pigeon breeders (N=55).

Social Skills	Occurrence	Percentage (%)
Communication	22	40.00
Co-operation	7	12.72
Problem solving	13	23.64
Responsibility	5	9.09
Social Awareness	8	14.55

Table 2. Occurrence of social skills and occupational self-efficacy among literate pigeon breeders (n =38).

Skills	Occurrence	Percentage (%)
Social Skills	32	84.21
Occupational self efficacy	36	94.74

Table 3. Occurrence of social skills and occupational self – efficacy among Illiterate pigeon breeders (n =17).

Skills	Occurrence	Percentage (%)
Social Skills	4	23.53
Occupational self - efficacy	5	29.41

Table 4. Difference between of social skills and occupational self – efficacy among literate and Illiterate pigeon breeders (n =55).

Skills	Occurrence on Literates	Occurrence on Illiterates	Difference	Percentage (%)
Social Skills	32	4	28	50.91
Occupational self – efficacy	36	5	31	56.36

Table 2 and 3 shows Occurrence of social skills and occupational self-efficacy among literate pigeon breeders and Occurrence of social skills and occupational self-efficacy among Illiterate pigeon breeders respectively. In this present study the results shows that occurrence of social skills and occupational self- efficacy were 84.21% and 94.74% . When it compared with illiterate pigeon breeders occurrence of social skills and occupational self- efficacy were 23.53% and 29.41%. Occupational self – efficacy is an important concept that can affect performance, results and behaviour. In a nutshell self- efficacy improves occupational performance. Ahamdi in his studies obtained the scores of ability to receive and send messages, emotional control, and listening skills higher than the average. Hajloo, (2011), in their study reported that a score of occupational self- efficacy of nurses was higher than the average value. Social skills and occupational self- efficacy are two important aspects in improving the pigeon farming. From this research it can concluded that social skills and occupational self- efficacy is closely related and they are dependent on each other to bring the pigeon keeping profession to a higher level through the pigeon breeders by maintaining the pigeon farming process as well as improving the quality of work.

Table 4 shows the difference between of social skills and occupational self- efficacy among literate and Illiterate pigeon breeders. The present study results shows the difference between of social skills and occupational self- efficacy among literate and illiterate pigeon breeders were 50.91% and 56.36% Respectively. Education has a strong correlation with socio-economic development. Defined socio economic status as an assessment of person's education, occupation and income position within a particular social system. Education is the one of the most important ingredients of human resource in today's high technological world and literacy is the real tool of extracting maximum benefits from the marvels of technology. Illiteracy and lack of basic education is not only a cause of poor living standard of people but also impedes a reasonable and stable progress. Literate pigeon breeders show more success in the pigeon farming business compared with illiterate pigeon breeders. Because pigeon farming business needs different areas of farm management like the business strategy and management, whole farm planning,

acquiring tools, equipments and infrastructure, raising livestock, marketing, accounting and financial management skills, decision making, risk management and specific technical skills. The well educated pigeon breeder may acquire the above mentioned skills through his course of study and he will succeed in his business. Personality traits and abilities may be to some extent inherited. But only with the education and continuous learning is possible to develop the necessary competencies of a successful pigeon breeders.

CONCLUSION

Pigeon farming is an emerging enterprise in Tuticorin District. Commercial squab production started in Tuticorin district then it gained popularly in squab meat is very lean, easily digestible and richer in protein, mineral and vitamins. It is also used as tasty, delicate and fancy meat. In Tuticorin district pigeon production in rural areas is of great importance as supply of meat and as source of income especially to young energetic people. The findings of the present study point out the importance of social skills in the pigeon farming. The importance of these skills, which contribute to success in life and occupational self- efficacy. The present study reveals the importance of communication skills and other social skills and also role of literacy on the success of pigeon farming business.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The authors would like to thank the pigeon loft owners and pigeon breeders who participated in this survey, Dr. P. Noel Kannan, well experienced and well known pigeon fancier, Nagercoil and Mr. Jegan, familiar fancy pigeon breeder in Tuticorin distict, for their valuable suggestions and technical support.

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